

Retrogradation of the Western Ganga-Brahmaputra Delta (India and Bangladesh) : Possible Reasons

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Abstract

Comparison of multidated maps / images, field evidence and a majority of the recent literature indicate that the Ganga-Brahmaputra delta (GBD), west of the river Haringhata, is retrograding for the last 200 years. The probable reason for this, according to the early workers (1858-1893), are: sediment trapping by the Swath of No Ground (SNG) submarine canyon, influence of 'tidal wave' and abandonment of the western distributaries of the Ganga. To these, the later workers (1927-1994) have added: coastal subsidence, the high regional tidal range and sediments absorption by the lower deltaic marshes and distributaries. Other possible causes include: sediment sink at the reservoirs of the Ganga catchment, sea level rise and deforestation of the coastal mangroves. While all these factors, with exception to the 'tidal wave' hypothesis, have certain merits, delta abandonment and sediment interception by the SNG probably are the most important. They together have increased the relative dominance of the erosive marine and atmospheric processes over the accretional fluvial processes at the western GBD. Around the Hugli estuary, a slow progradation of the subaqueous delta is seen although the terrestrial part is getting eroded.

INTRODUCTION

Situated at the northern apex of the Bay of Bengal, the Ganga-Brahmaputra delta (GBD) is the world's largest both in terms of land area (c. 150×10^6 km²) and yearly discharge of sediments ($\sim 1 \times 10^9$ t), derived from a catchment area of 1.55×10^6 km². The delta is a composite one, formed by the Ganga, Brahmaputra and many small to medium sized peripheral rivers that emanate from the surrounding uplands. Of these, the Meghna is the largest (Fig. 1A). The current orientation of the Ganga-Padma-Lower Meghna river diagonally divides the GBD into two halves. The southwestern half, along with southern coastline of the delta

Fig. 1: (A) Drainage area of the Ganga-Brahmaputra Delta (GBD). Numbers identify the sub-catchments of the Ganga (1), Brahmaputra (2), Meghna (3) and the west-bank tributaries of the Bhagirathi-Hugli (1a). Locations of some of the major dams have also been given.

(B) Physical setting of the western GBD. Hatching indicates hilly areas. The location of the Farakka barrage, main tributaries of the Bhagirathi-Hugli and the deltaic distributaries of the Ganga-Padma system have also been shown. River names : A Ajay; D = Dwarka; M = Mayurakshi, and R = Rupnarayan.

between the Hugli and Haringhata, has mostly been contributed by the distributaries of the Ganga system (Fig. 1B) active or dissipated. This 220-km coastal stretch constitutes about 52 per cent of the GBD coastline and has been referred to as the western sector of the GBD in this paper. In it, the Ichhamati-Hariyabhangra river forms the boundary between the Indian and Bangladeshi portions of the delta (Fig. 2C). Among the 13 major tidal channels that funnel out into the Bay of Bengal through the western GBD, only the westernmost Hugli and Baratala have any sizable connection with the upland river sources. In the rest, the Indian rivers of Saptamukhi, Jamira, Matla, Bhangaduni and Gosaba are maintained completely by the tide and the Hariyabhangra, Malancha, Kunga, Pushur, Bangra and Haringhata of Bangladesh have only feeble connections with deteriorated former outlets of the Ganga (plate 1, Fig. 1B and 2C).

Radiocarbon dates from the Indian part of the GBD have indicated a Late Holocene age of around 3,000 yr. for its coastal formations (Gupta, 1981; Chakrabarti, 1991a). While a number of excellent works now exist on the evolution of the delta or part of the delta up to that period (Niyogi, 1975; Banerjee, 1984; Banerjee and Sen, 1987; Umitsu, 1987, 1993; Alam, 1989), hardly any has specifically addressed the problems of the delta's coastline evolution during the last couple of hundred years. The present paper is an endeavour to fill up this gap, even if partially. It is mainly based on analysis of the available literature and data, supplemented by comparison of multidated maps/images and additional information from field evidence.

Mapping of the Coastal GBD

Though there are instances of a few bathymetric charts of the Hugli estuary from the end of the 17th century, a surveyed map for the whole of the GBD did not appear prior to J. Rennell's 1778 *Bengal Atlas* (Sheet No. 1; 760,321). As Carr (1962) and deBoer and Carr (1969) have noted, even in Britain, a pioneer country in cartography, reliable maps and charts hardly date back to the start of the 19th century—the time when triangulation survey was introduced in India (Gole, 1978). However, Rennell's work, although prepared by somewhat crude techniques (Fawcus, 1927) and by route surveys, immediately became 'the standard map of Bengal for more than 50 years' (Gole, 1978:78) and is still widely used as the earliest basis for comparative cartographic studies of the delta face. The next depiction of the delta front, subsequent to Rennell (1778), was R. Lloyd's 1842 *Sea Face of the Soondurbans* (1:253,440), based apparently on astronomical observations, and it was not until the first decade of 29th century, when triangulated bathymetric-cum-seaface charts, produced by the Hooghly River Survey Department (RSD), became available (Reaks, 1919). Systematic land surveys, however, were more regular and reasonably accurate maps of the coastal

Plate 1 : One of the earliest satellite records of the western GBD, this image (Landsat MSS, date of pass : 21 Feb 1973) shows the absence of link between the westernmost distributaries of and the trunk river (not in the image). See Fig. 1C for identification of the estuaries and islands. (Image courtesy: J. Sen).

delta, on 1:253,440 were available from the 1870s. Among these, two useful publications were the maps produced by H. L. Thuillier and R. L. Thuillier in 1874 and 1889 respectively. The first 1:63,360 toposheet representing part of the western delta coast (No. 79C/14) was published by the Survey of India (SoI) in 1908 and the entire stretch was covered by 1924. These one inch maps ran up to two to three revised editions during the following two decades.

The presently available Indian maps on the Indian part of the GBD coastline are quite dated. For instance, the delta-front represented in the 1988 maps of *National Atlas of India* (Sheet Nos. 15 and 33, on 1:1,000,000, 2nd edition) was taken from the 1922-23 and 1942 surveys with only the position of the recently emerged Purbasha (New Moore) island added subsequently! Even the latest large scale toposheet of the SoI (1:50,000), which replaced the earlier one-inch series, were surveyed in 1968-69. (The area has not yet been covered by the newer 1:25,000 series). Not only the delta coast has markedly shifted since this time (Fig. 2D), but also many of the estuarine and outer islands shown in these maps have undergone significant changes in area and position. Consequently, SoI aerial photos (scales

ranging from 1:25,000 to 1:40,000) and satellite images (Landsat, SPOT and IRS-1: 1:50,000 to 1:1,000,000) are now the only means for studying the comparatively recent positions of the delta face. However, because of the technical difficulties involved in preparing an undistorted true-to-scale mosaic of a very large area (that too without any cultural landmark) from satellite images, an available 1984 mosaic prepared by the Geological Survey of Bangladesh and the United States Geological Survey (Alam *et al.*, 1990) has been used in this study (Fig. 1C).

THE PROBLEM OF NON-PROGRADATION OF THE DELTA FRONT

Literature Review

Sherwill (1858) was probably the first worker to deal with the problem of the growth of the GBD. He had stated the sediment discharge rate of the Ganga-Brahmaputra as $1,133 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. Taking inference from the Po (Italy) and Thames (Britain), he had estimated that, other things being equal, during the interval taken for the Po delta to form, the Sandheads (westernmost GBD) should have prograded some 800 km into the sea. He had also identified the Swatch of No Ground (SNG), a 200 km U-shaped submarine canyon that cuts across the GBD shelf to reach 30 km off the Kunga estuary, as the principal silt-trapper, retarding delta growth.

Prior to Sherwill (1858), Rennell (1781:266) had observed that, 'the sands and mud banks ... extend twenty miles [i.e., 32 km—we now know that they extend up to 55 km] off some of the islands in the mouths of the Ganges and the Burrampooter; and rise in many places within a few feet of the surface. Some future generation will probably see these banks rise above water, and succeeding ones possess and cultivate them!' About 80 years later, basing on contemporary charts of the Bay face and comparing them with earlier maps, Fergusson (1863:47–8) had concluded that, though the eastern half of the GBD is 'in a state of rapid change', 'little or no change or extension seaward has taken place during the last 100 years' in the western sector between the Hugli and Haringhata (Fig. 1B). Drawing analogy from the Nile, he had speculated that the 'tidal wave' (by tidal wave he probably intended to mean the crest of a high tide) coming from the east being 'larger' than the one coming from the western portion of the delta had 'sufficient force to fix the seaward limit of the western Sundarban' (p. 50). On the other hand, the northward indentation of the coast in the eastern delta, Fergusson (1863) believed, was due to the silt absorption from the Brahmaputra by the Sylhet marshes through which this river once used to flow (see Morgan and McIntire, 1959:331 for details). He had presumed that, by the middle of the 20th or 21st century, with the progress in the infilling of the marshes, the condition would change, and the delta front would form a nearly straight, E-W coastline. This, of course, has not been realised to date.

While R. D. Oldham (1893:411) had agreed with Fergusson's (1863) conclusions on the link between the delta growth in the eastern sector and the sedimentation by the Brahmaputra, he had felt that the western sector was not prograding because, through it only 'a small portion of flood water of the great rivers finds its way to the sea'. Obviously, he had related the near-absence of siltation in the western part of the delta to abandonment of the Ganga distributaries – a fact highlighted earlier by T. Oldham (1870).

Fawcus (1927) had observed that a comparison between the Rennell's map and the 1906 topographical maps denote an eroding coastline. The anomaly between the two maps, according to him, is so great that it cannot be explained alone by inaccuracy in mapping methods of Rennell; some other cause like very recent subsidence of the littoral zone, should also be considered.

Strickland (1940), however, had subsequently placed the rate of deltaic accretion above the rate of subsidence and opined for a prograding delta face. Majumdar (1942), on the other hand, had thought, since Rennell's time the two extremes of the face of the GBD might have prograded but not the central portion. Bagchi (1944:71), had concluded that, while 'it is really difficult to say anything conclusively ... it is sufficiently clear that Rennell's survey might not have been so accurate as to think that there has been no accretion of land since his map was prepared.

The interesting thing is that Reaks (1919) had already superposed and compared the maps of Ritchie (1970: *Chart of Western Seaface*), Lloyed (1842) and the Hooghly River Survey Department (1910) for the entire delta face and had clearly brought out the eroding nature of the western delta. The Reaks' maps (two of which appear as Fig. 2A and 2B) somehow have remained completely obscured to the later workers and while some of them have taken into account or have reasoned for the general non-prograding nature of the delta (Morgan and McIntire, 1959, Coleman, 1969; Chakraborty, 1970; Basu and Chakraborty, 1972; Eysink, 1983; Kuehl *et al.*, 1989; Bridges, 1990; Basu, 1992; Basu and Sen, 1994 and the other works cited above), it is comparatively recently that the eroding nature of the delta or parts of the delta has been started to be recognized both in India and in Bangladesh (Stoddart and Pethick, 1984; Chakraborty *et al.*, 1987; Paul and Bandyopadhyay, 1987, SPARRSO, 1987 in Das and Khan, in press; Bandyopadhyay, 1990, 1993, 1994; Bandyopadhyay and Chakraborty, 1990; Mafizuddin, 1990; Chakraborty, 1991; Chakraborty, 1991b; Paul, 1991, present volume; Banerjee, 1992; Bandyopadhyay *et al.*, 1993; Das and Khan, 1993; Pal and Roy, 1993). However, in spite of all these studies, which are mostly based on field evidences or superposition of multidated maps and images, a number of authors still maintain that the GDP is prograding or has not eroded at all. For example, Ahmad

(1972 : 105) has ascertained that 'however slow the process of accretion, there are clear geomorphic evidences of land building' off the Sagar island. Bird (1985 : 111-2), reviewing global coastline changes, has observed that the GBD is one of the 'chief prograding sectors' in the east coast of India. Similar views have also been held by Spate and Learmonth (1967), Bose (1979), Ahmad (1985), Chattopadhyay (1985), Mandal and Ghosh (1989), Das (1992), Mukherjee (1993), Singh (1993) and Basu and Sen (1994). It might be noted that the conclusions of these studies have largely been based on prevailing conceptions and none of the works have employed any kind of periodic surveys or measurements.

Localities and Estimates of Deltaic Erosion

From Multipurpose Cyclone Shelter Project (MCSP)-related studies in Bangladesh, erosion has been found to be most noticeable along the western part of the GBD coastline (Khulna district) between 1971 and 1991. In some places, coastal retreat has been as high as a kilometre in the 20-year period. The study also identified the Ganga-Brahmaputra estuary (called Meghna estuary in Bangladesh) and the off-shore islands in the easternmost part of the GBD as the zone where some stable accretion has taken place (Das and Khan, in press). In a separate, study, SPARRSO (1987 in Das and Khan, in press) has estimated that in the Bangladeshi portion of the Sundarban, nett loss of land area has been 115.36 m² in the 24 year period between 1960 and 1984 (Table 1A).

There has hardly been any systematic estimation of this kind for the Indian section of the GBD. However, some estimates do exist for its reclaimed (western-most) part—all of which indicate a general erosive character (Table IB). Superimposed multidated maps and images of the western delta face (Fig. 2) as well as field evidences like basally eroded frontal dunes (Plate 2) and erosional clay banks are also indicative of on-going erosion in the forested (eastern, Bangladesh-adjacent) sectors of the Indian GBD coast.

Summary of the Factors Affecting Delta Growth

Various reasons have been put forward by different workers to account for the non-prograding nature of the western GBD—some of which have already been introduced. A list of these factors has been provided in Table II for easy references. A few other possibilities have also been suggested at the end.

THE FATE OF THE SEDIMENTS CONTRIBUTED BY THE GANGA-BRAHMAPUTRA AND BHAGIRATHI-HUGLI

The continental shelf off the GBD extends for some 75 km into the sea and its 'clinoform-like' morphology is comparable to the shelves occurring at the mouths of other major rivers. The Ganga-Brahmaputra and the Bhagirathi-Hugli, at the easternmost and westernmost part of the GBD, are the modern-day sediment

Fig. 2 : Superposed maps and images of various years connote that the coastline of the western Ganga-Brahmaputra delta, except for a few localities, is retrograding for the past several years. Island names : B = Bakkhali; C = Chuksar, E = Edmonstone, J = Jambu, N= New, P = Purbasha or New Moore, S = Sagar, and T = South Talpatti (Source : A : Fig. 1 of Reaks, 1919; B : Fig. 6 of Reaks, 1919; C : Sol sheet nos 79C and 79G (both 2nd edition) reduced to 1:1,000,000 and Alam, et al., 1990; D : Fig. 6.6 of Bandyopadhyay, 1994).

Plate 2 : Wave-erosion of frontal dunes, indicating coastal retreat, is common in many parts of the Indian sector of the western GBD. This sequence from Shibpur, Sagar island, represents complete obliteration of a foredune in three years. Note left-ward shift in view-point between August, 1990 and February, 1991 photos, indicated by the triangles.

Table IA : *Accretion and Erosion of the Coastal Ganga-Brahmaputra Delta : Bangladeshi Part*

Period / Source		Region	Accretion (in km ²)	Erosion (in km ²)	Net gain (=)/loss (-) (in km ²)
1960-1984 (SPARRSO, 1986 in Das and Khan, in Press)	I.	Mainland coastal area	881.07	1734.66	- 853.59
	II.	Islands of the Ganga- Brahmaputra estuary (Sandwip, Hatia Bhola and Manpura)	52.24	263.16	- 211.92
	IIIa.	Delta face between the Haringhata and Hariyabhanga rivers (Sundarban)	30.34	145.69	- 115.36
	I + II + IIIa	—	963.65	2143.51	- 1180.87
1971-1991 (MCSP, 1992 in Das and Khan, in press)	IIIb.	Same as IIIa, above	14.45	74.73	- 60.28

Table IB : *Accretion and Erosion of the Coastal Ganga-Brahmaputra Delta : Indian Part*

Period	Source	Method	Migration of high tide line	Maximum retreat of coastal dune belt due to wave erosion
<i>I. Bakkhali coast (between Baratala and Saptamukhi estuaries : 5 km)</i>				
1968-89-1988	Chakrabarti (1991b)	Comparison of Sol sheet no. 79C/6 (1968- 69, 1:50,000) and aerial photos (1975, 1:25,000) with GSI beach maps (1:5,000)	250 m (landward, parallel retreat	—
1985-1989	Bandopadhyay and Chakraborty (1990)	Seasonal beach mapping (on 1:5,000) and profiling	4 m-107 m	51.5 m
1986-1992	Pal and Roy (1993)	as above	4 m-107 m	—
<i>II. Sagar island coast (between Hugli and Baratala estuaries : 11 km)</i>				
1986-1992	Pal and Roy (1993)	Seasonal beach mapping (on 1:5,000) and profiling	8 m-38 m (seaward western part) 19 m (landward, eastern part)	25 m

Continued

Period	Source	Method	Migration of high tide line	Maximum retreat of coastal dune belt due to wave erosion
1991 (Apr)- 1993 (Jan)	Bandyopadhyay <i>et al.</i> (1993)	as above	—	10.9 m
1922-23-1992	Bandyopadhyay (1993, 1994)	Comparison of Sol sheet no. 79C/2 (1992- 23, 1:63,360) with IRS- IB LISS-II SFCC (21 Feb 1992, 1:50,000)	—	0-1750-m (landwards) Area gained : + 0.10 km ² area lost : -8.41 km ²

Note : GSI = Geological Survey of India, IRS= Indian Remote Sensing Satellite, Sol = Survey of India, LISS = Linear Image Self Scanner, SFCC = Standard False Colour Composite

Table II : *Factors affecting Non-progradation of the Western Ganga-Brahmaputra Delta, India and Bangladesh*

I. Suggestions of the early workers

1. Off-shore sediment trapping by the Swatch of No Ground submarine canyon (Sherwill, 1858)
2. Influence of the 'tidal wave' (Fergusson, 1863)
3. Sediment absorption by the Sylhet marshes (affects the eastern GBD only) (Fergusson, 1863; Oldham, R. 1893)
4. Low sediment-input from the western distributaries of the delta due to natural shift in their prominence (delta abandonment) (Oldham, T., 1870; Oldham, R., 1893)

II. Suggestions of the later workers

5. Regional to local subsidence (Fawcus, 1927; Morgan and McIntire, 1959; Rudra, 1986; Alam, 1989; Basu, 1992)
6. The high regional tidal range (Ray, 1966; Petts and Foster, 1985).
7. A modification of Fergusson's (1863) idea, envisaging a low sediment-input from the Ganga's-western distributaries as a consequence of its absorption in inland depressions/ marshes of the mature part of the delta (Chakraborty, 1970, Basu and Chakraborty, 1972; Basu, 1992) and/or in-channel sedimentation of the tidal distributaries (Basu and Sen, 1994).

III. To these, some other possible causes might be added

8. The man-induced silt-traps in the form of many dams and reservoirs in the catchment of the Ganga system.
9. Positive relative sea level change in the last 200 years caused by factor(s) apart from subsidence.
10. Decline of the coastal mangroves due to reclamation of the coastal Sundarban.

contributors to the shelf region. There are, however, two principal departures, firstly, according to the existing literature, there is no active subaqueous delta present (Kuehl *et al.*, 1989) and, secondly, a deep submarine trough, the SNG, cuts across the shelf to reach within 30 km of the coast (Fig. 3; see Rao, 1988, p. 6 for details on the SNG).

Sediments from the Ganga-Brahmaputra

The estimation of the suspended sediment discharge of the Ganga-Brahmaputra (lower Meghna) river has been estimated from $1,667 \times 10^6$ t yr⁻¹ (Milliman and Meade, 1983) to $2,180 \times 10^6$ t yr⁻¹ (Holeman, 1968; Lisitzin, 1972. See Table III), making it the world's largest sediment contributor to the sea.

Gibbs (1981) has estimated that, at sediment input rate of $2,270 \times 10^6$ t yr⁻¹ (this value also includes contributions from the Damodar and Mahanadi), the continental shelf off the Ganga-Brahmaputra should be filled-up up to 100 m isobath within 2,630 years which, however, might extend to 3,410 years if sediment compaction and loading subsidence is taken into consideration. Kuehl *et al.* (1989:1135), considering the area of the Bangladesh portion of the continental shelf, have assessed that, at the sediment input rate proposed by Milliman and Meade (1983), 'the entire shelf would fill to sea level in less than 1 ka (one thousand years) assuming no sediment bypassing from the shelf occurred and that regional subsidence was negligible.

The average sedimentation rate over the entire area off the Ganga-Brahmaputra has been indirectly reckoned by Gibbs (1981) at 19 mm yr⁻¹. Comparatively, Kuehl *et al.*'s (1989) estimation (21-86 mm yr⁻¹) is higher than this. Because the data of Kuehl *et al.* are based on direct core sample analysis, the latter estimate seems to be more reliable than the former. Kuehl *et al.* (1989:1135) have felt that 'there has been ample time since the sea level stabilised about 6 ka (six thousand years) to have accretion of the subaqueous delta to the shelf break', which, of course, has not taken place. From grain size analysis and dating of sediment cores and grab samples from the shelf to the east of the SNG, they have shown that the accumulated shelf sediments, the dispersal of which is limited to ~80 m, have a tendency to move towards the west from the Ganga-Brahmaputra estuary during the high energy conditions between May and September. The SNG, where the sediment accumulation rate has been found to be the highest (86 mm yr⁻¹ at c. -20 m at the head of the canyon compared to two other sites along the shelf where the rates have been 64 mm yr⁻¹ at c. -50 m and 21 mm yr⁻¹ at c. -80 m), intercepts this transportation and acts as a passage (Fig. 3) for southward bypassing of the river sediments into the deep sea Bengal fan. Earlier, Coleman (1969) had thought that, because the tidal current ridges of the GBD shelf have a tendency to curve towards the SNG, *they* probably act as sediment passages from

Fig. 3 : Shelf bathy-orography off the GBD showing position of the Swatch of No Ground submarine canyon and its role as a sediment sink. Arrows indicate net sediment influx and movement. Isobaths are in metre. SNG = Swatch of No Ground.

the river-mouths to the canyon-head. The facts that the mineralogy of the Indian shelf sediments to the west of the SNG can be correlated with the loads of the local rivers (Rao *et al.*, 1988 in Kuehl *et al.*, 1989) and that the input of sediments into the SNG comes mainly from the eastern parts rather than from the west (*Marine Wing News Letter*, 1987) seem to support the conclusions of Kuehl *et al.* The comparatively coarser grain size of the SNG floor than that of its enclosing areas is also suggestive of sediment movement along the canyon (Sengupta *et al.*, 1992).

However, Sengupta *et al.* (1992) have also found from mean grain size distribution and dispersion pattern studies, that the GBD shelf sedimentation to the west of the SNG takes place mainly from the northeast. If the model of Kuehl *et al.* (1989) is to be accepted, then these sediments should be explained as have passed north of the SNG and therefore have avoided interception.

Table III : Drainage Area, Water and Suspended Sediment Discharge of some Selected Rivers of the Ganga-Brahmaputra delta

River	Source	Drainage area (km ²)	Average water discharge (10 ⁶ m ³ yr ⁻¹)	Average suspended sediment discharge (10 ⁶ t yr ⁻¹)	Storage capacity of the major reservoirs in the catchment (10 ⁶ m ³)	
Ia	Ganga at Farakka	Rao (1975)	—	459,040	—	28,514.9
Ib	Ganga at Farakka	Abbas and Subramanian (1984)	648,000	459,000	801.00	—
<i>Input from tributaries :</i>						
Ila	Mayurakshi-Dwaraka	Rao (1975)	8,850	4,687	—	554.6
Ilb	Ajoy	Rao (1975)	6,050	3,207	—	nil
IIIa	Bhagirathi-Hugli at Calcutta	Abbas and Subramanian (1984)	750,000	—	411.00 ¹	—
IIIb	Bhagirathi-Hugli at Calcutta	WRI (1992)	748,634	314,400	411.00	—
<i>Input from tributaries :</i>						
IVai	Damodar	Holeman (1968)	20,000	10,000	28.00	—
IVaii	Damodar at Rhondia	WRI (1992)	20,000	9,800	31.28	—
IVaiiii	Damodar	Rao (1975)	25,820	12,210	—	3,398.8
IVb	Rupnarayan	Rao (1975)	8,530	4,400	—	nil
IVc	Kangsabati-Haldi	Rao (1975)	10,210	5,300	—	972.4
IV	IVaiiii + IVb + IVc	Rao (1975)	—	44,560	21,910	—
Va	Hugli below Haldi (at confluence)	Rao (1975)	861,404	493,400	—	—
Vb	IIIb + IV	Rao (1975) and WRI (1992)	793,194	336,310	440.00–481.00 ²	4,961.2 ³

River	Source	Drainage area (km ²)	Average water discharge (10 ⁶ m ³ yr ⁻¹)	Average suspended sediment discharge (10 ⁶ t yr ⁻¹)	Storage capacity of the major reservoirs in the catchment (10 ⁶ m ³)	
VIa	Ganga-Brahmaputra	Holeman (1968)	—	—	2,180.00	—
VIb	Ganga-Brahmaputra	Lisitzin (1972)	—	—	2,180.00	—
VIc	Ganga-Brahmaputra	Coleman (1969)	—	—	980.00	—
VI d	Ganga-Brahmaputra	ECI-ACE (1970 in Milliman and Meade, 1983)	—	—	835.00	—
VIe	Ganga-Brahmaputra	Subramanian (1978)	—	—	1,180.00	—
VI f	Ganga-Brahmaputra	Gibbs (1981)	—	—	2,270.00 ⁴	—
VIg	Ganga-Brahmaputra	Milliman and Meade (1983)	1,480,000	971,000	1,667.00 ⁵	—
VIh	Ganga-Brahmaputra	WRI (1992)	1,480,000	970,000	1,746.40	—

- Notes: 1. In this, the share of chemical load is 83×10 yr. Measured during monsoon, 1981.
 2. These are minimum and maximum values of projected estimations. See text for explanation.
 3. Data only for the west-bank catchment of the Bhagirathi-Hugli.
 4. Includes the Damodar and Mahanadi.
 5. Milliman and Meade (1983) have estimated that in 1970 this exceeded $2,000 \times 10^6$ t.

Source: Bandyopadhyay, 1994.

Sediments from the Bhagirathi-Hugli

The western part of the GBD has been subjected to comparatively lower silt replenishment than the eastern sector during the last few centuries mainly because of natural factors such as decaying of the western distributaries of the Ganga and also due to man-induced factors like construction of reservoirs on the west-bank tributaries of Bhagirathi-Hugli. This, as already stated, had been linked to the non-progradation of the GBD first by Oldham (1983) and subsequently by other workers.

Abbas and Subramanian (1984) have calculated that while the sediment load of the Ganga at Farakka is $801 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$, it gets reduced to $411 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$ along the Bhagirathi-Hugli at Calcutta. This, understandably, is largely contributed by the western tributary basins of the Bhagirathi (the Mayurakshi and Ajay: having a combined basin area of $14,900 \text{ km}^2$) as well as the seasonal augmentation from the Farakka project (see Begum, 1988; Basu and Ghosh, present volume; Fig. 1A). The sediment load data of the major rivers that join the Bhagirathi-Hugli downstream of Calcutta (the Damodar, Rupnarayan and Haldi : Fig. 1B) are not available at their respective confluences (Table III). Together these rivers occupy a large catchment area of $44,560 \text{ km}^2$ and have an installed storage capacity of $4,370.8 \times 10^6 \text{ t}$, distributed in four major reservoirs (Rao, 1975), which act as major silt traps. For example, the life of the largest of these reservoirs at Maithon in the Damodar catchment (capacity: $611.84 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$) has been estimated at 246 years by the Damodar Valley Corporation.

The discharge data of the Hugli at its estuary below the Haldi as given by Rao (1975: $493,400 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$) seems to be questionable. This is because, the discharge of the Hugli at Calcutta (WRI, 1992: $314,400 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$) and the combined discharge of all the major tributaries that fall into it below the city (Rao, 1975: $21,910 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$) together fall short of Rao's estimate by $157,100 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$. (rows Va and Vb, Table III). This anomaly is too large to be accounted for contributions from surface runoff and the minor channels downstream of Calcutta. Thus, a conservative estimate of $336,310 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$ should represent a more realistic picture (row Vb, Table III). Projecting the estimated load of the Hugli at Calcutta ($411 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$), as given by Abbas and Subramanian (1984) and WRI (1992), to this revised discharge data, sediment contribution of the Hugli to the Bay of Bengal may be put at $440 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$. However, if Holeman's (1968) and WRI's (1992) data on the sediment discharge of the Damodar (rows IVai and IVai, Table III) are projected to the three tributaries of the Hugli downstream of Calcutta, this figure increases to $473 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$ and $481 \times 10^6 \text{ t yr}^{-1}$ respectively. Among these, the conservative estimates of the Hugli's water and sediment discharge amount approximately to a quarter and a one-third of that of the Ganga-Brahmaputra

respectively (Milliman and Meade's estimate: row VIg, Table III). It may be noted here that the sediment contribution from the Hugli, though considerably smaller than from the main (eastern) outlet of the GBD, is by no means insignificant. Apart from the Hugli and Baratala, the six large medium-sized estuaries to the east of the Gosaba, which have feeble connection with up-country streams, also contribute some sediments to the sea which are, however, relatively quite small.

It follows that if the *low sediment input from the western distributaries* model is to be linked to the coastal erosion of this part of the delta, then, the present sediment contribution from the Hugli has to be taken as not enough for arresting the process of retrogression. Alternatively, *the sediment bypassing of the shelf area* model, like the eastern section of the delta, has to be applied here also. Although the SNG would have a small role to play in a model like this, it is possible that, following the trend of environmentally similar eastern GBD shelf, here too the sediments have a nett tendency to move westwards and away from the delta region (Fig. 3).

Development of the Subaqueous Part of the Westernmost GBD

Apart from comparing the coastal maps, Reaks (1919) had also considered the evolution of the submarine GBD, especially of the western part of it. He took the 5-fathom (9.44 m) isobath as the foundation of the delta and noticed rapid general progression (up to 10 km in some parts) in the subaqueous part of the western delta off the Hugli estuary and Sagar island for the 70-year period between 1770 and 1840 and a comparatively slower progress for the next 70 years between 1840 and 1910. He, however, had admitted that since the Ritchie's 1770's bathymetric survey was not very accurate, it had to be 'adjusted' at a few places. Reaks (1919:38) had concluded that, in spite of the coastal erosion, 'the delta forming functions of the Hugli ... are by no means inactive'.

As has appeared from similar comparative study by Chakrabarti and Sen (1972) extending up to the 60 feet (18.3 m) isobath, for the subsequent 40-year interval between 1910 and 1950, the slow progradation of the submarine delta has remained mostly unchanged. It should be stressed, however, that these studies only involved the area off Sagar island and any generalisation is therefore not possible.

According to Chattopadhyay (1985:221), 'recently, it has been detected from satellite photographs that a submerged platform skirts the delta head for a considerable distance southward on which the Jambu ... and Purbasha (islands) are emerging with possibility of many more being added to the list'. He has concluded that, although some authors have suggested a non-prograding nature of the delta, this 'clearly establishes an advancing delta head' to the west of the Hariyabhanga, compared to the stretch to its east. Despite an apparent similarity

between the thinking of Chattopadhyay and the studies based on comparative bathymetry, it seems doubtful whether the penetration capability of any satellite can yield information on submarine platforms in the highly turbid off-shore water condition of the GBD that shows up prominently as suspended sediment plums of different densities in most satellite false colour composites. As revealed by chronological study of maps for the last 150 years, small outer islands of the coastal GBD (Fig. 1C) like Chuksar, Edmonstone, Jambu, Purbasha (also called New Moore) and South Talpati are inherently transitory and ephemeral in nature and they, instead of the sea-facing coastline of the main islands between the tidal estuaries, cannot be used to indicate 'an advancing delta head' as attempted by Chattopadhyay (1985:221).

DISCUSSION

While shelf bypassing of the river sediments may conclusively explain the non-advancement of the delta face, it cannot explain the erosion *per se*.

A delta is a product of interaction between the primarily accretional fluvial (discharge/load) processes and mainly erosional marine and tidal processes (Elliott, 1986), with its exact nature also depending on other factors like relative sea level (RSL) change and natural hazards. In the western GBD, the erosional tidal-marine processes are now dominating over the accretional fluvial processes. This tide-dominated delta (mean spring range is 4.3 m at the mouth of Hugli: SoI, 1992) is also open to a large fetch and is prone to highly destructive tropical cyclones (IMD, 1979). For example, the Bangladeshi part of the GBD has been struck by seven of the world's nine deadliest storms of this century (Cobb, 1993). With the decrease in cumulative accumulation and/or replenishment, factors like these have reciprocally become more prominent and have increased the delta's vulnerability to long term erosion. A contrast can be cited in the microtidal Godavari delta (in the east coast of India), where, despite the sediment input being just a quarter of the amount discharged by the Bhagirathi-Hugli (96×10^6 t yr⁻¹: Milliman and Meade, 1983), a prograding delta front has been maintained (Vaidyanadhan, 1991) due to the relative dominance of the accretional fluvial processes.

World examples, relating diminished riverine sediment input to non-progradation or erosion of delta faces, are many. As Bird (1985) has shown, in deltas such as the Huanghe (China), Rio Sinu (Colombia), Ceyhan (Turkey), Cimanuk (Indonesia), and Medjerda (Tunisia), with changing outlet positions, the abandoned parts of the deltas have been subjected to erosion. The entire western sector of the GBD (with the exception of the section around the Hugli estuary) can be classified as the abandoned part of the delta as far as sediment input is concerned and this alone should conveniently explain its eroding nature. As seen

earlier (Table II), the non availability of sufficient amount of sediments in the western delta can be linked to a number of natural factors. These include the gradual diversion of the Ganga's discharge through the Padma (presently the main distributary of the Bangladesh) and degradation of the Bhagirathi-Hugli since the early 16th century (Rudra, 1986); in-land (marshes/depressions) siltation by the delta distributaries and interception of sediment accumulation by the SNG.

Among the man-induced factors, instances of delta retardation after construction of dams/reservoirs upstream are also commonplace (Petts, 1984; Bird, 1985; Carter, 1988; Stanley, 1988). Parts of the Nile delta have registered erosion rates as high as 30 m yr⁻¹ after completion of the Aswan High Dam in 1964. According to Carter (1988:483), the main distributary of the Nile, the eastern Damietta, 'is now almost dry; while the western distributary, the Rosetta, supports a much reduced flow relative to that in historical times. Sediment supply has fallen from 120 × 10⁶ t yr⁻¹ before 1964 to 50 × 10⁶ t yr⁻¹, leading to progressive shoreline change including erosion ... and ... local accretion (from dispersing erosion products)'. Similar examples can also be cited in the deltas of the Rhone (France), Dnipro (Ukraine), Dniester (Ukraine), Volga (Russia), Volta (Ghana), and Zambezi (Mozambique) (Bird, 1985). While the building of vast storage capacity on the rivers of the Ganga and Bhagirathi-Hugli systems (Table III) and consequent diversion of water for irrigational uses cannot be directly related to the coastal erosion of the GBD, a positive inference through their effect as silt trappers can probably be drawn in view of the experiences elsewhere. It may be mentioned here that, in other humid tropical areas (Af and Am climates), deltas have shown accelerated progradation in response to deforestation and farming (Bird, 1982). So, a possibility exists that these activities in the down-dam areas may have somewhat offset the silt trapping effect of the reservoirs.

Goodess *et al.* (1992) and Gornitz (1993) have considered that the best estimates of the rate of secular sea level change for the last 100 years range from 1 to 2 mm yr⁻¹. At this rate the sea level was some 100 to 200 mm lower than its present position about 100 years ago and near about double that amount 200 years earlier. Other parameters like subsidence of the lower delta during this interval could have even increased this figure, effecting an RSL change of some significance. Because there are much conclusive evidence of autocompaction-related subsidence in the coastal region of the GBD in the form of buried organic and cultural horizons (see Table I of Morgan and McIntire, 1959 and Table 1 of Sen and Banerjee, 1990), a positive RSL change might have played a role in the erosion of the delta face. The fact that 70 per cent of the world's sandy coastlines are eroding for the last few decades and that this trend, in all probability, can be attributed to the Holocene rise of the sea level (Bird, 1985), and corroborates this

observation. It might be mentioned here that although a number of studies now exist on the possible transgression of the coastal GBD due to a rapid future rise in the sea level caused by man-induced global warming (Milliman *et al*, 1989; Saha, 1991; Broadus, 1993), no clear evidence of any accelerated sea level rise could be detected from the region till date (Brammer, 1990).

It is doubtful whether the deforestation of the coastal mangroves and the erosion in the lower GBD are related phenomena. This is because, in the GBD, it has been seen that, both the reclaimed and the forested areas (Sundarban) are equally prone to shoreline erosion. Thus, deforestation might have somewhat increased the rate to coastal erosion, but it definitely has not caused it.

While a large tidal range can have a bearing on coastal erosion by adding to the dominance of the marine agencies, a link between 'tidal waves', and coastal retardation, as proposed by Fergusson (1863), seems far fetched. It must be borne in mind that the western GBD once accreted under the very similar tidal and climatic conditions as today. As was observed by Reaks (1919:77), Fergusson 'appears to have been misled by taking the times of high water instead of the directions of the currents at different points to show the approach of the wave'. The ocean current in the Bay of Bengal moves clockwise in the winter half of the year and anti-clockwise in the summer half (Walker, 1983). So, the proposition of two bi-directional tidal waves, with which Fergusson had also tried to explain the formation of the SNG and has later been supported by authors like Hirst (1915) and Chakraborty (1970) seems untenable.

CONCLUSIONS

In final review, it seems that all the factors outlined in Table II, with exception to Fergusson's (1863) 'tidal wave' hypothesis, have something to contribute to the general non-progradation and regional retardation of the GBD. The most important among them are probably the abandonment of the sediment replenishing western distributaries of the Ganga and off-shore interception of westward sediment transportation by the SNG. Together these factors have made the erosive marine and tidal processes more dominant than the accretional fluvial processes at the western GBD. Overall, a loss in the terrestrial part of the western delta front and a gain in the subaqueous part (at least up to 1950) off the Hugli estuary are observed. The reason for the latter must be the fact that the Hugli (including its eastern branch Baratala) is the only river in this sector that contributes a sizable amount of sediment to the sea.

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